

Responses Overview Active

Responses

19

Average Time

17:44

Duration

82 Days

1. Select the typology of organisation you belong to (select one):

- National Public Administration 3
- Local/Regional Administration 3
- Private company 3
- Small medium enterprise 2
- Large enterprise 0
- University / research centre 7
- NGO / professional association 1
- Other 0

2. Primary role of your company in the data ecosystem (select one or more)

- Data provider (urban sensors, BIM models, cadastre, GIS, etc.) 6
- Infrastructure designer / data architect 4
- Technical operator (connectors, brokers, data platforms) 3
- Urban planning or smart city manager 2
- Digital twin or GIS-BIM project manager 5
- Policy-maker / public regulator 1
- Data provider/user (analyst, consultant, developer) 4
- Research 7
- Standardization body 2
- Other 3

3. Main area of action (select one or more):

- Urban or territorial planning 7
- Agriculture 2
- Smart cities (mobility, energy, water, climate, etc.) 6
- Construction and infrastructure (BIM, GIS-BIM) 9
- Local or regional public administration 4
- Projects 7
- Digital twin pilots 6
- Other 2

4. Your Age

- Less than 20 0
- 20 - 29 1
- 30 - 39 6
- 40 - 49 2
- 50 - 59 7
- More than 59 3

5. Select your role within your organisation (Select your role within your organisation)

- Manager 5
- Technician 7
- Researcher 7
- Policymaker 0
- Other 0

6. Which is your country?

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Latest Responses

- "Spain"
- "Spain"
- "Ukraine"
- ...

9 respondents (47%) answered spain for this question.

7. What data activities do you perform or coordinate in your organisation (select all that apply)?

Yes No I don't know

8. Other data-related activities carried out or coordinated within your organisation

5 Responses

Latest Responses

2 respondents (40%) answered Data for this question.

Identity management
 Data Infrastructure
 Data conector
Data
 Spatial

No

conector development
 Spanish

9. What is the level of knowledge you have on data space or digital twins?

High Medium Under Null Not applicable

10. Are you currently involved in any projects related to data spaces or digital twins?

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Responses

Latest Responses
"No"
"The National Spatial Data Infrastructure"
...

4 respondents (31%) answered yes for this question.

11. What technical or management activities do you or your team perform regarding urban data/digital twins? (Select all that apply)

- Data Access (from heterogeneous sources) 12
- Cataloguing and publication data (metadata, DCAT) 10
- Data transformation and harmonization (ETL, APIs, vocabularies) 15
- Use of semantic models (ontologies, data alignment) 10
- Ensuring traceability and data lineage (logging, versioning) 4
- Define usage agreements and exchange conditions 6
- Not any 1
- Other 0

12. What technical or management activities do you or your team perform regarding data space? (Select all that apply)

- Data sharing with third parties (connectors, brokers) 11
- Define usage agreements and exchange conditions 9
- Orchestrating data flows in a data space 7
- Not any 4
- Other 0

13. What is the level of knowledge you (or your team) currently have for these activities?

High Medium Under Null Not applicable

14. For the Data Access (from heterogeneous sources) activities you perform, what knowledge or skills do you consider necessary? (You can write several for each role or select from a suggested list below)

- Standard data model (INSPIRE) 11
- OGC standards 13
- Open BIM 12
- Formats and protocols for data exchange (e.g., ISO/IEC 11179, ISO 19115, W3C standards) 12
- JSON, XML, CSV, RDF, IFC 15
- APIs and data access protocols 15
- Not any 0
- Other 0

15. For the data Cataloguing and publication activities you perform, what knowledge or skills do you consider necessary? (You can write several for each role or select from a suggested list below)

- Metadata standards (DCAT, Dublin Core, ISO19115)) 15
- Data Discovery and Cataloguing Tools (CKAN, DataHub, Amundsen, Apache Atlas) 6
- Data catalog integration (API,...) 14
- Standards for Data Publication (FAIR, LOD, Open Data) 12
- Not any 0
- Other 3

16. For the Data transformation and harmonization activities you perform, what knowledge or skills do you consider necessary? (You can write several for each role or select from a suggested list below)

- Data mapping from differed sources 17
- Data modeling (JSON, GeoJSON, XML) 14
- Not any 0
- Other 3

17. For the semantic modelling activities you perform, what knowledge or skills do you consider necessary?
(You can write several for each role or select from a suggested list below)

● Knowledge of sectorial ontologies	11
● Use of standard vocabularies	15
● Linked data	12
● Not any	3
● Other	0

18. For the Data sharing with third parties activities you perform, what knowledge or skills do you consider necessary?
(You can write several for each role or select from a suggested list below)

● Connectors	16
● Brokers	5
● Not any	3
● Other	1

19. For the Ensuring traceability and data lineage activities you perform, what knowledge or skills do you consider necessary?
(You can write several for each role or select from a suggested list below)

● Data Lineage Tools & Frameworks	9
● Logging and Monitoring Systems	8
● Knowledge of Database Formats and Metadata Technologies	17
● Not any	0
● Other	0

20. For the Define usage agreements and exchange conditions activities you perform, what knowledge or skills do you consider necessary?
(You can write several for each role or select from a suggested list below)

● Data Governance Act, Data Act, Open Data Directive	14
● GDPR	10
● Licensing and rights management (es. Creative Commons)	10
● Not any	1
● Other	0

21. For the Orchestrating data flows in a data space activities you perform, what knowledge or skills do you consider necessary? (You can write several for each role or select from a suggested list below)

22. What type of skills do you consider to be the most difficult to find or fill in your organisation? (Select up to 3)

23. Which of the following training course formats do you consider most useful for improving these competences?

24. Which kind of certification would you like to be provided?

25. Which best describes the current state of the data space in which your organisation participates?
(Choose the one that comes closest)

26. What challenges do you foresee in the next 2 years to advance to the next level? (Select up to 3)

27. What additional expertise do you see as key to improving the maturity of data space?

28. Would you be interested in participating in pilot initiatives or co-creation groups to develop these capacities?

- Yes, in cooperation with other cities / regions 8
- Yes, within my own organisation 5
- No, for the moment 6

